

SYNTHESIS OF THE ALICYCLIC SYSTEMS RELATED TO THE STEROIDS. PART II

BY PHANINDRA CHANDRA DUTTA

A method has been successfully developed for the synthesis of the tricyclic systems comprising B, C, D rings and the angular methyl group, which is capable of extension to the tetracyclic systems.

In part I of this series (Mitter and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1948, 26, 210) several attempts have been made with a view to working out a general method for the synthesis of the alicyclic systems and the one, which was expected to be a promising one, had failed so far as the removal of the quaternary carboxyl group is concerned.

In the present investigation, a method has been successfully developed to build up the tricyclic system as represented below.

Ethyl methylcyclopentanone carboxylate is brominated in dilute ethereal solution in the cold and the bromo compound is converted into the unsaturated compound (I) on heating with quinoline. The reaction leads to the formation of a considerable amount of tar and the unsaturated compound is obtained in a moderate yield. With aluminium isopropoxide this is reduced to the hydroxy-ester (II, R=OH), which is probably contaminated with the corresponding isopropyl ester due to *trans*-esterification. With phosphorus tribromide, this is converted into bromide (II, R=Br). The estimation of halogen shows that the conversion is about 90% of the theoretical.

The idea underlying the introduction of the double bond is to activate the halogen atom in (II, R=Br). It is evident from the observation of Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 60) that in the corresponding saturated ester the replacement of the hydroxyl group with halogen will not only be far from satisfactory, but the reactivity of the same

will also be very poor. Another view is to leave some possibility for the introduction of a substituent in the methylene group, the so-called C_{17} -position, through bromo-succinimide for the development of the characteristic side-chain. The bromo-ester is condensed with cyclohexanone in dilute ethereal solution in presence sodamide and the keto-ester (III) is obtained in a poor yield. This is reduced catalytically, and the product on hydrolysis gives the corresponding acid (IV) in a moderate yield. It is converted into acid chloride and this condenses readily with ethyl magnesio-malonate in ethereal solution. The crude condensation product is hydrolysed with acetic acid and hydrochloric acid mixture. The hydrolysis is found to proceed with considerable tarrification. The yield of the diketone (V) is very poor, which is quite unexpected in this method of synthesis for methyl ketones. The analysis of the product shows too high value for carbon, from which it is suspected that the product has undergone partial ring-closure with the elimination of water leading to the formation of (VI). This assumption appears to be more probable when it is found that on very careful fractionations, the product can be separated into two fractions differing greatly in carbon values in analysis. The partial ring-closure during hydrolysis is further corroborated by the fact that reduction with aluminium isopropoxide always leads to epimeric mixtures (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2022). The *cis*-compounds under conditions of hydrolysis generally show a tendency towards ring-closure and several examples have been cited by Liustead in the series of investigations on 'Fused rings'. The combined fractions are dehydrated in boiling benzene solution with sodamide and the unsaturated tricyclic ketone (VI) is obtained as a faint yellow liquid, which turns greenish on standing. To determine the stereochemical configuration with respect to the cyclopentane ring, the product is oxidised with nitric acid and from the butyl alcoholic extract, an oily acidic product is obtained which fails to crystallise on standing.

Another method of approach to this problem has been designed in the following manner, which can be schematically shown below.

The halogen atom of ethyl 2-bromocyclohexylidene-acetate (Mitter and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) behaves like α -halogen atom and condenses smoothly with ethyl methylcyclopentanone carboxylate in presence of magnesium according to Haberland (*Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1215). The hydroxy-ester (VII) is isolated in a moderate yield, which shows no tendency to lactonisation probably owing to the presence of *trans*-configuration (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2123). Attempts to dehydrate the product (VII) leading to the formation of the doubly unsaturated ester (VIII) by heating with potassium hydrogen sulphate, anhydrous oxalic acid or phenyl isocyanate (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 704) have met with failure. Partial success has, however, been effected by heating with *p*-tolylsulphonic acid and the unchanged hydroxy-ester is separated later on through catalytic reduction due to appreciable difference in boiling points. The catalytic reduction of the hydroxy-ester in acetic acid leads mainly to the formation of the lactone (XII), together with a small quantity of the saturated hydroxy-ester. This indicates that during reduction, the acetic acid chain is oriented mainly to the *cis*-position with respect to the cyclopentane ring. The lactone resists all attempts at reduction under standard methods and heating of the same with thionyl chloride and subsequently with alcohol leads to complete tarrification instead of the formation of the unsaturated ester (X, R=Et) (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2061). The impure, doubly unsaturated ester is catalytically reduced in acetic acid solution, whereby the saturated compound (IX, R=Et) is separated from other products through careful fractionation and is finally obtained in a pure condition in a poor yield. This on treatment with sodium dust in boiling benzene gives a product, which is directly hydrolysed with dilute sulphuric acid. It is found that most of the product has been converted into high boiling residues, together with a small fraction passing over at the expected boiling range. This fraction gives a dirty green ferric chloride reaction in alcoholic solution, showing thereby that the β -ketonic system in (XI, R=Et) has not been completely hydrolysed. The analytical values of the fraction also supports this view. One of the reasons for this variation may be due to the presence of different stereoisomers showing different rates of hydrolysis, the presence of which has already been indicated during catalytic reduction.

To facilitate the course of hydrolysis and to minimise the formation of high boiling residues in Dieckmann's condensation, it is desired to repeat the experiments with the corresponding methyl ester (IX, R=Me). To prepare this compound, the catalytic reduction product from the hydroxy-ester (VII) is directly treated with thionyl chloride and pyridine in ethereal solution and finally the crude product is hydrolysed with methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide according to Bachmann (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2580). From the alkaline solution a fraction, neutral in character, has been isolated which can again be separated into two fractions. The analytical data and boiling points of these two fractions could give no indication regarding their probable structures. The acidic fraction is isolated on acidification and the separated oil on esterification with methyl alcohol gives the expected methyl ester (X, R=Me) in a poor yield. It turns slightly coloured on standing and takes up hydrogen rather slowly leading to the formation of the saturated ester (IX, R=Me). This is allowed to react with sodium

methoxide in benzene solution (Bachmann, *loc. cit.*). On working up the product, the desired β -ketonic ester (XI, R=COMe) is isolated in a moderate yield, together with a high boiling residue remaining in the flask. This β -ketonic ester fails to give any ferric chloride coloration. On hydrolysis with acetic and hydrochloric acids, a fraction has been isolated having the expected boiling point and a strongly camphoraceous odour, but the analytical data for carbon is again found to be too low. Moreover, the ketonic group could not be further characterised by any functional derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 5-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenon-5-carboxylate (I).— Ethyl methylcyclopentanone carboxylate (20 g.) was dissolved in dry ether (200 c.c.) and cooled in ice. Bromine (20 g.) was added drop by drop with shaking. There was rapid decolorisation. On pouring the mixture in ice-water, the ether layer was separated, washed with water and sodium bicarbonate solution. On drying and distillation, it passed over at 128° - $131^\circ/8$ mm. as a light yellow heavy oil with a pungent odour, yield 25 g. The bromo-ester (21 g.) was mixed with freshly distilled quinoline (12.6 g.) and gradually heated to 160° in an oil-bath in an atmosphere of nitrogen, when a vigorous reaction started. It was maintained at that temperature for 15 minutes and then cooled rapidly and decomposed with ice. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, followed by sodium carbonate solution. On distillation, the unsaturated ester passed over at 95° - $100^\circ/10$ mm. as a mobile liquid which soon turned greenish yellow on standing. On redistillation, it boiled at 99° - $102^\circ/10$ mm, yield 9 g. (Found : C, 63.6 ; H, 7.86. $C_9H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 64.2 ; H, 7.2 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Methyl- Δ^2 -cyclopentenol-5-carboxylate (II, R=OH).— Aluminium foils (2 g., 2 mols.) were dissolved in dry isopropyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and mercuric chloride (1 g.) by refluxing for 7 hours. Next it was diluted with isopropyl alcohol (30 c.c.) and the above keto-ester (10 g.) in isopropyl alcohol (30 c.c.) was added. The mixture was heated in a glycerine-bath (100° - 105°), when isopropyl alcohol gradually distilled off. Again isopropyl alcohol (25 c.c.) was added and distillation continued. Finally the temperature was raised to 125° in the glycerine-bath. The total duration was about 7 hours. On cooling, the mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and on working up the product, a fraction boiling at 105° - $115^\circ/9$ mm. (mainly at $108^\circ/9$ mm.) was collected, yield 9 g. [Found : C, 61.6 ; H, 8.8. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 60.7 ; H, 8.9 per cent. $C_9H_{16}O_3$ (isopropyl ester) requires C, 62.7 ; H, 9.3 per cent].

5-Methyl-5-carbethoxy- Δ^2 -cyclopentenyl Bromide (II, R=Br).— The unsaturated hydroxy-ester (16 g.) was dissolved in benzene (50 c.c.), to which pyridine (1 c.c.) was added. It was cooled in a freezing mixture and stirred. Phosphorus tribromide (5 c.c.) in benzene (15 c.c.) was added gradually in the course of an hour and after the addition was complete, it was allowed to attain the room temperature. It was then decomposed with ice and extracted with benzene. The benzene layer on drying with calcium chloride turned greenish. During the removal of benzene on the water-bath

there was a copious evolution of hydrobromic acid gas and the residue on distillation gave the bromo compound boiling at 108° - $113^{\circ}/8$ mm. (mainly at $111^{\circ}/8$ mm.) as a yellowish pungent liquid, yield 11 g. [Found : Br, 29.4. $C_9H_{13}O_2Br$ requires Br, 34.3 per cent. $C_{10}H_{15}O_2Br$ (isopropyl ester) requires Br, 32.6 per cent].

2-(2'-Methyl-2'-carbethoxy- Δ^4 -cyclopentenyl)-cyclohexanone (III).—Finely powdered sodamide (1 g.) was covered with dry ether (60 c.c.), to which cyclohexanone (3 c.c.) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours with vigorous stirring. Next it was further diluted with ether (20 c.c.) and the solvent was distilled off so that the volume was reduced to half. It was then cooled in ice and the above bromide added and after 15 minutes, it was refluxed for 2 hours, and finally the volume was reduced to half again. On working up the reaction mixture, the product was distilled in vacuum and a fraction (1 g.) was obtained boiling at 140° - $145^{\circ}/3$ mm. as a clear oil with a reddish tinge. On redistillation, it passed over at 130° - $135^{\circ}/2$ mm. (Found : C, 72.4 ; H, 8.6. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 72.0 ; H, 8.8 per cent).

2-(2'-Ketocyclohexyl)-1-methylcyclopentyl-1-carboxylic Acid (IV).—The above ester (1 g.) was reduced in acetic acid with platinum catalyst (1 g.) and the hydrogenation was complete in 10 minutes (Ca: 180 c.c.). On working up the product, a fraction was obtained as a clear colorless oil boiling at $150^{\circ}/8$ mm. This was hydrolysed with caustic potash (0.8 g.) and methyl alcohol (5 c.c.) by refluxing for 10 hours on the water-bath. The neutral portions were removed and the acidic fraction, on distillation in high vacuum was obtained as a viscous mass (0.7 g.) boiling at 135° - $140^{\circ}/0.02$ mm. It did not solidify when kept at -10° for a week. (Found : C, 69.3 ; H, 9.3. $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 69.6 ; H, 8.9 per cent).

2-(2'-Methyl-2'-acetylcyclopentan-)-cyclohexanone (V).—The keto-acid (0.54 g.) was dissolved in ether (5 c.c.) and pyridine (0.5 g.) and thionyl chloride (0.5 c.c.) were added and the mixture was allowed to stand in the cold. After 2 hours it was thoroughly cooled when pyridine hydrochloride solidified and the acid chloride decanted off. The residue was washed with dry ether. The solvent was removed and benzene added which was again distilled off to remove thionyl chloride. Next it was dissolved in dry ether and added to a solution of magnesium (0.2 g.) and malonic ester (1.2 g.) in ether. On addition it was allowed to stand overnight and next day it was refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours. It was decomposed with ice and acid and extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent, the residue was hydrolysed with a mixture of acetic acid (5 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) for 16 hours. There was considerable tarrification. It was extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and finally distilled in vacuum, when a fraction (0.2 g.) was obtained boiling at 100° - $105^{\circ}/0.02$ mm. with a rosy tinge and gave the following analytical data. (Found : C, 77.58 ; H, 9.63. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 75.7 ; H, 9.8 per cent).

This fraction was again distilled when two fractions were collected :

(I) 95° - $100^{\circ}/0.02$ mm. (major fraction) : (Found : C, 76.4 ; H, 9.9%).

(II) 90° - $95^{\circ}/0.02$ mm. (minor fraction) : (Found : C, 77.9 ; H, 9.3%).

1: *2-cyclopentano-2-methyl-3-keto- Δ^4 -octalin* (VI).—The above two fractions (140 mg.)

were dissolved in benzene (4 c.c.) and to the solution was added powdered sodamide (55 mg.). It was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours. On decomposing it with ice and hydrochloric acid it was extracted with benzene and again with ether. On removal of the solvent the reddish residue was distilled, when an oil (40 mg.) passed over at 100° - 110° /0.02 mm. (bath temperature, 120° - 130°) with a greenish tinge. There was a residue in the flask. It had a characteristic camphoraceous odour. (Found : C, 81.6 ; H, 10.0. $C_{14}H_{20}O$ requires C, 82.2 ; H, 9.9 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(1'-Hydroxy-2'-methyl 2'-carbethoxycyclopentan)-cyclohexylidene- acetate (VII).—*cyclo*Hexenyl acetic ester was prepared by dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine of the hydroxy-ester obtained from the reaction of *cyclo*hexanone and bromoacetic ester in presence of zinc. The unsaturated ester was allowed to react with one molecule of bromine, followed by treatment with sodium methoxide in the cold. From the reaction mixture the unsaturated bromo-ester was isolated in a moderate yield. A mixture of bromo-ester (20 g.), methyl*cyclopentan*one carboxylic ester (20 g.) and toluene (75 c.c.) was added to dried magnesium (9 g.) covered with toluene (20 c.c.) in a 250 c.c. flask, to which a mixture of methyl iodide (5 c.c.) in ether (10 c.c.) was already added. All the components were freshly distilled. The reaction flask was placed in a glycerine-bath at 60° . Vigorous reaction started which was maintained by gradually raising the temperature to 120° after an hour. After 2 hours it was stopped when most of the magnesium went into solution. The Grignard's complex was decomposed with ice and ammonium chloride and subsequently acidified with ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The reaction product was extracted with toluene and the solvent was recovered in water-suction. On distillation, the lower boiling fractions were rejected and the fraction boiling at 145° - 175° /3 mm. was collected, which on redistillation passed over at 155° - 165° /2 mm. (mainly at 160° - 165° /2 mm.) as a light yellow oil, yield 9.5 g. (Found : C, 67.48 ; H, 8.86. $C_{18}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 67.4 ; H, 8.9 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(2'-Methyl-2'-carbethoxy- $\Delta^{1:5}$ -cyclopenten)-cyclohexylidene-acetate (VIII).—The above hydroxy-ester (5 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 170° - 180° for 15 minutes with *p*-tolylsulphonic acid (1.2 g.) when the mass turned black. On cooling immediately it was worked up and extracted with ether. On removing the acidic impurities it was distilled, when a clear mobile oil (3 g.) was collected boiling at 140° - 150° /2 mm. which turned coloured on standing. On careful fractionation a small quantity of a high boiling fraction was separated and the doubly unsaturated ester (1.5 g.) was obtained boiling at 145° - 150° /2 mm. (Found : C, 70.4 ; H, 8.5. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 71.2 ; H, 8.7 per cent).

Ethyl 2-(2'-Methyl-2'-carbethoxycyclopentan)-cyclohexyl Acetate (IX, R=Et).—The above unsaturated ester (4.5 g.) was reduced catalytically with platinum oxide catalyst (0.2 g.) in acetic acid solution. Absorption of hydrogen was about 300 c.c. (theoretical, 600 c.c.) in about two days. Catalyst was removed and on distillation the saturated ester was obtained as a colorless oil boiling at 140° /2mm., yield 2.3 g. There was a considerable high boiling residue. (Found : C, 70.1 ; H, 9.6. $C_{19}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 70.4 ; H, 9.8 per cent).

Lactone of 2-(1'-Hydroxy-2'-methyl-2'-carbethoxycyclopentan)-cyclohexane Acetic Acid (XII).—The hydroxy-ester (VII, 4 g.) was reduced in the usual way. When absorption was complete, it was worked up and on distillation two fractions were obtained. Fraction (I) came at 150° - $155^{\circ}/2$ mm. (2.8 g.) and another fraction (II) passed over at $165^{\circ}/2$ mm. (0.6 g.). Fraction (I) gave the following analytical values. [Found : C, 69.3 ; H, 8.3. $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ (lactone) requires C, 69.3 ; H, 8.8 per cent]. Fraction (II) gave the following analytical values. [Found : C, 67.0 ; H, 8.9. $C_{16}H_{22}O_5$ (hydroxy-ester) requires C, 67.1 ; H, 9.4 per cent].

Action of Sodium on the Saturated Diester.—The saturated diester (IX, 2 g.) was heated with sodium dust (0.3 g.) in benzene (30 c.c.). In 3 hours the whole of the sodium went into solution. It was then decomposed with ice and dilute acid and the residue left on evaporation of the solvent was refluxed for 16 hours with dilute sulphuric acid (15 c.c., 30%). On working up in the usual way, a small fraction (0.3 g.) was isolated, which boiled at 125° - $135^{\circ}/3$ mm. and showed a dirty green coloration in alcohol with ferric chloride solution. It gave the following analytical data. [Found : C, 78.2 ; H, 10.4 ; $C_{14}H_{22}O$ (ketone) requires C, 81.5 ; H, 10.6. $C_{17}H_{26}O_3$ (β -keto-ester) requires C, 73.4 ; H, 9.4 per cent].

Methyl 2-(5'-Methyl-5'-carbomethoxy- Δ^1 -cyclopentenyl)-cyclohexyl Acetate (X, R = Me).—The unsaturated hydroxy-ester (VII, 5 g.) was catalytically reduced and on removal of the acetic acid and subsequent drying, it was treated with thionyl chloride (5 c.c.) and pyridine (7 c.c.) in ether (20 c.c.), cooled in ice. After an hour, ethereal solution of hydrogen chloride was added to precipitate pyridine. The ethereal layer was decanted off, the solvent and the low boiling impurities were removed in the pump. The residue was heated with dimethylaniline (5.5 g., 3 mols.) at 160° for half-an-hour and at 180° - 190° for half-an-hour more. On working up the mixture, it was distilled, when a fraction (3 g.) was obtained boiling at 150° - $160^{\circ}/3$ mm. which contained halogen. So it was refluxed for 10 hours with a solution of caustic potash (5 g.) in methyl alcohol (50 c.c.). The solution was diluted with water and methanol was removed on the water-bath. The neutral portion was taken with ether and the acidic portion was isolated on acidification and esterified with methyl alcohol (10 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) and a fraction (0.3 g.) was isolated boiling at 130° - $135^{\circ}/3$ mm.

Another lot from the catalytic reduction of the unsaturated hydroxy-ester (10 g.) was refluxed with a solution of caustic potash (10 g.) in methyl alcohol (100 c.c.) for ten hours (after thionyl chloride treatment in the same manner and using the same proportions). The methanol was removed and the residue was heated for two hours with a solution of potassium hydroxide (100 c.c., 30%). The cooled solution was diluted with water and extracted with ether, which removed the neutral fraction. The alkaline portion on acidification gave an acidic portion, which on esterification with methyl alcohol (30 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (4 c.c.) for 3 days gave the desired methyl ester (2.3 g.) boiling at 132° - $135^{\circ}/3$ mm. It assumed a greenish tinge on standing for a few days. (Found : C, 69.3 ; H, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 69.3 ; H, 8.9 per cent).

The neutral fraction (4 g.) was again separated into two fractions :

(I) B. p. 92° - $95^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, 79.1 ; H, 10.5%).

(II). B. p. 125° - 130° /4 mm. (Found : C, 75.3 ; H, 10.8%).

The unsaturated methyl ester (X, R=Me) gave the following data. (Found : C, 69.3 ; H, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 69.3 ; H, 8.9 per cent).

Methyl 2-(2'-Methyl-2'-carbomethoxycyclopentyl)-cyclohexyl Acetate (IX, R=Me).—The above unsaturated ester (2.2 g.) was reduced catalytically in acetic acid solution with PtO_2 catalyst. Absorption of hydrogen was slow and the saturated ester was isolated in the usual way, b. p. 130° - 135° /4 mm., yield 2 g. (Found : C, 69.2 ; H, 9.6. $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 68.7 ; H, 9.4 per cent).

1:2-cycloPentano 2-methyl-3-keto-4-carbomethoxy-decalin (XI, R= CO_2Me).—The above ester (2 g.) was treated with sodium methoxide from sodium (0.25 g.) in benzene (25 c.c.) and refluxed on the water-bath for 6 hours in nitrogen atmosphere, when whole of sodium methoxide went into solution. The solution was worked up in the usual way and on distillation, a fraction (8 g.) was isolated at 130° - 140° /3 mm. which gave no coloration with ferric chloride. (Found : C, 72.7 ; H, 9.6. $C_{18}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 72.3 ; H, 9.1 per cent).

Attempted Hydrolysis of the above Ester.—The above ester (0.8 g.) was hydrolysed with acetic acid (12 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (12 c.c.) for 12 hours under reflux. From the reaction mixture, the neutral fraction (0.3 g) was obtained boiling at 125° - 130° /3 mm. having a characteristic odour and gave the following analytical data. [Found : C, 79.1 ; H, 10.2. $C_{14}H_{22}O$ (ketone) requires C, 81.5 ; H, 10.6 per cent].

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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